

EXAMINATION OF SURGICAL PATIENTS

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Annotation: As we all know, inspection (inspection) is the examination of the patient's appearance and general condition, body structure, condition of the skin and visible mucous membranes. This article talks about the methods of examining surgical patients.

Key words: Objective examination methods, additional examination methods, coma, sopor, stupor, consciousness, facial expression.

INTRODUCTION : You need to ask important questions to find out what patients need, and then we need to carefully investigate. You should look for signs that help determine whether the patient's condition is severe or mild. There are specific questions and methods for each patient. These include the symptoms that the patient himself notices and the symptoms that you find during the examination. In the case of people who cannot speak and babies, these signs are very important.

MAIN PART: Examination (inspektion) - the patient's appearance and general condition, body structure, skin and visible mucous membranes are determined during the examination.

The appearance and general condition of the patient can be as follows: satisfactory, moderate, severe, very severe.

The patient's status can be as follows: active (active), passive and forced. If the patient is lying down, but he can turn from one side to the other, sit down, stand up, this condition is called active. If the patient cannot move, cannot turn over, cannot raise his head or hand, and lies in any position, then this position of the patient is called a passive position.

When the patient tries to relieve his suffering, and takes some kind of situation, it is called a forced situation. For example, patients with shortness of breath lean on the edge of the bed with their hands and sit in a forced position with their legs hanging down. Patients with bronchial asthma, gastric ulcer perforation, peritonitis, appendicitis, pericarditis, pleurisy and other diseases fall into a forced position.

Transition of patients from passive to active state indicates recovery of patients, on the contrary, if patients transition from active to passive state, patients are observed to worsen or relapse of the disease. For example, patients with tumors and cancer can change from an active state to a passive state.

Objective verification methods are divided into two types. These are: basic and additional methods. The main inspection methods include:

- review;
- palpation - feeling;
- percussion - knocking;
- auscultation — hearing;

- additional verification methods include:
- inspection using equipment;
- laboratory testing.

Coma is a complete loss of consciousness due to damage to brain centers that are important for life. In a coma, muscles relax, sensibility and reflexes disappear, there is no reaction to any impact - pain, light, sound. Coma occurs in cases of cerebral hemorrhage, diabetes, severe liver damage, chronic nephritis, and poisoning.

Sleep is a state of sleep. If the patient is awakened by loud calling or pushing, he can answer questions and then fall back into a deep sleep.

Stupor is a state of numbness, in which the patient is vaguely aware of the surrounding situation, answers questions reluctantly and late.

Patients have varying degrees of nausea. In addition to the loss of consciousness, changes in the central nervous system are also observed. These include delusions, hallucinations, which occur when the body temperature rises during infectious diseases, severe sweating, and rash.

Facial expression. When examining a patient, it is important to pay attention to his facial expression, because the facial expression usually reflects the patient's condition. An old facial expression indicates that the patient is suffering from severe pain, and on the contrary, a fresh, calm expression of the face indicates that the person is in a good condition. In some cases, facial expression helps to identify the disease. For example, swelling of the face in the morning, especially in the area of the lids, gives reason to think that the kidneys are infected, the lids can also swell in anemia, trichinellosis, myxedema, and angina.

In severe heart diseases, the face becomes pale, the mucous membrane of the lips, the soft part of the ear, the tip of the nose turns blue, the mouth is open, and the patient seems to be gasping for air. Patients with severe acute pain in the abdominal organs (for example, peritonitis caused by perforation of a stomach ulcer) have the typical expression described by Hippocrates: the appearance of the face is sharp, the eyes are sunken. sunken, his face looks tired, his skin is grey, and a cold sticky sweat comes out of it.

The facial expression of patients with epilepsy is characteristic. In this case, due to the simultaneous contraction of all the muscles of the face, the mouth widens as if laughing, wrinkles appear on the upper part of the face and forehead, as if a person is sad (sardonic laughter), the facial expression of patients with tuberculosis it will be unique, pale, the cheeks of the face will be red, the eyes will be wide open, the pupils will be large, the sclera will be blue.

The facial expression of people suffering from endocrine disease is characteristic: for example, the shiny eyes are squinting and the person looks as if he is afraid of something for Basedov's disease, the round moon-like redness of the face with a bluish tint, in women, in addition, hair growth on the upper lip and chin is typical for a pituitary gland tumor (Isenko-Cushing's disease).

Enlargement of the lower jaw, cheekbones, browbones, large nose, large drooping ears, and thick lips are characteristic of acromegaly.

Drooping eyelids in paresis or paralysis of the optic nerve: Drooping eyelids indicate major changes in the brain. Nystagmus, i.e. non-stop vibration movement of the eyelid in the horizontal plane, is observed in some diseases of the brain, in ear diseases accompanied by disorders of the labyrinth function, and in diffuse or multiple sclerosis. Fixation of the eye to one point without moving is observed in patients with meningitis.

CONCLUSION: In conclusion, despite the fact that there are many new examination methods, especially instrumental examinations, the classic examination of the patient, that is, questioning and physical methods, has not lost its relevance.

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